

Thermal Image Stitching for Improved Quality Control in Thermoforming Machines

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Abstract. The thermoforming process is associated with both environmental sustainability and cost-effectiveness in the industrial sector. This study addresses the comprehensive analysis of the heat distribution patterns of polymer materials undergoing thermoforming in a production line environment. A change in temperature during the heating process on the polymer material has the possibility of causing inconsistencies and errors in the material. The Zero Defects and Zero Waste (ZDZW) Horizon Europe project aims to develop a suite of services designed to reduce errors and waste in industrial environments. One among these services is the implementation of thermal inspection application. Within the scope of this project, data obtained from thermal cameras placed in refrigerator production lines where thermoforming application is used. An inspection software solution is proposed that aims to create entire thermal distributions of polymer parts using thermal image stitching method on this data. The proposed software solution focuses on enabling real-time thermal inspection through precise thermal image stitching.

Keywords: Thermal Inspection · Image Stitching · Computer Vision.

1 Introduction

The thermoforming process is generally used for thermoplastic materials; however, it might also be used for thermoplastic-based composite materials [1, 2]. In addition to the characteristic features of these materials such as recyclability, and not requiring storage in demanding conditions, the thermoforming process is preferred in many different sectors such as white goods, small household appliances, and automotive due to its cheap and fast mass production [3-5]. This method consists of three main stages: heating, molding, and cooling the plastic [4]. During the molding stage, the softened material is generally inflated into the mold under negative pressure, and the mold is closed. Although heating is generally provided by radiation thanks to resistance heating, some mold structures also provide heat transfer by conduction in the process [6]. The variations

in temperature during the heating phase can lead to inconsistencies in material behavior and the formation of defects in the final formed parts [7]. The presence of manufacturing defects in thermoforming processes can be minimized through the implementation of adjustments to the process factors, including the initial heating temperature profile, forming speed and the introduction of simplifications to the geometry [8]. To fulfill this challenge, it is essential to conduct an inspection of the processed material on the thermoforming production line to ensure the sustainability of the process.

The Zero Defect and Zero Waste (ZDZW) Horizon Europe project, which is funded by the European Union, has the objective of developing non-destructive inspection thermal applications that will be interoperable in production lines, with the aim of reducing defects and waste. The aim of this study is to apply the control software solution to thermoforming machines in refrigerator production lines. As seen in the Figure 1, the polymer part goes through preheating and forming stages on the thermoforming line. Preheating is the first heat treatment applied to the polymer part. The molding stage forms the heated polymer part. The thermal inspection software observes the process that takes place between these two stages. The non-destructive solution is expected to extract the thermal temperature distribution of the polymer parts on the line after the preheating application. Thermal cameras are used to extract this temperature distribution. In thermoforming lines, where the distance between the preheating and molding stages is limited, it is not possible to see the entire polymer part at once. Therefore, an image stitching algorithm has been added to the software solution.

Fig. 1: Thermoforming Production Line with Thermal Inspection.

The main objective of this study is to propose a software solution that includes image fusion technique for extracting thermal distributions of the entire surface of the polymer part in thermoforming lines.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the background and a review of the relevant literature. Section 3 outlines the methodology of the proposed approach. Section 4 presents the numerical results and offers an evaluation. Section 5 provides a conclusion to the paper.

2 Literature Review

In the studies conducted so far, there is a relationship between the thermoforming line and the thermal distribution of the processed part. The studies show how the stages should be heated. Prior to the forming stage, the thermoforming molds should be heated to a temperature exceeding the softening point of the polymer film. Following the forming stage, the molds should be cooled below the softening point to facilitate the de-molding process [9]. Applications that optimize the thermoforming line have used thermal cameras to extract the thermal distribution [8]. In the previous studies, the thermal imaging method used to calibrate the thermoforming stage is prepared in a laboratory environment and adjusted to see the entire part.

The quality control domain is currently undergoing a period of expansion and evolution within the industrial sector [10]. At this time, image processing techniques are among the most frequently used methodologies within this domain. One such technique is image stitching, which is a frequently used method in areas where a wide-angle, high-resolution image is required [11]. Cases where the part cannot be seen in a single frame are one of these cases. In thermoforming applications, situations where the working area is narrow and inaccessible are frequently encountered. In order to overcome the disadvantage of thermal heat distribution in these areas, it is important to extract it using the image stitching method so that the entire part can be analyzed.

As mentioned in Wang et al. (2020), there is currently no common method for stitching all image types due to image complexity [11]. The image stitching method varies for each domain and application area. For example, steal-beam defect detection [12], micro-hardness profile defect detection [13], plane or 3-D models [14] applications use a different image stitching technique for each. Classical image stitching methods consist of the following stages: image preprocessing, image registration, feature point extraction, and image fusion. The feature point extraction stage consists of Harris corner detection, SURF and SIFT algorithms [15]. Polymer sheets have a uniform and similar distribution in the thermoforming line. For this reason, the challenge of studying the feature extraction stage is explained in detail in the Methodology section. In addition, previous studies have been performed using visible cameras. In this study, the stitching process of thermal images on the thermoforming line is investigated.

3 Methodology

In the course of developing the image stitching algorithm, scenarios were constructed in accordance with the constraints inherent to the nature of the work. In order to realize these scenarios and create a dataset similar to the real test data, a test environment was first established. Thereafter, image stitching techniques were emphasized on these datasets in a way that would be most suitable for real data. As a result, the algorithm development process continued. This chapter will be analyzed under the following subheadings: Data Preparation, Image Stitching Techniques, and Algorithm Development.

3.1 Dataset Preparations

The initial stage of the data preparation process entailed an in-depth examination of the actual data set to gain a comprehensive understanding of its intrinsic characteristics. Following an examination of the environment in which the data was collected, studies were conducted to determine the optimal configuration for the office environment. In the test environment, the following equipment was utilized: a PI-640i Optris brand thermal camera, a tripod, a heater, and a 15 cm x 10 cm plastic piece. The image of the thermal camera mounted on a tripod is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Thermal Camera Setup of Experimental Setup.

A mechanism for movement was constructed so that the object would enter the camera frame at the bottom and exit at the top. With the assistance of a sizable envelope, the component was positioned on the envelope's surface and imaged in a repetitive manner.

Initially, the component was subjected to heating via the application of a heat source, namely a heater, and was then positioned on the aforementioned large envelope. Subsequently, the thermal camera was oriented at an angle of 70 degrees relative to the surface on which the part was to be maneuvered. Due to the diminutive dimensions of the part, the camera was situated at a distance of 40 cm from the table. This is a notable discrepancy from the actual data. This is because the parts to be examined in real data are of a considerable size, rendering their use in a test setup in an office environment impractical. Consequently, the test setup was devised to minimize both the size of the part and the distance between the camera and the part.

The data sets were obtained in the test environment through the use of a thermal imaging camera and a monitor, wherein the live image was simultaneously projected. This approach enabled the recorded data to be observed on the monitor, allowing for adjustments to be made during the recording process as necessary. The test data was created by extracting sections from approximately ten minutes of recorded footage.

The test data was obtained in two distinct modes. The first is the 30 Hz mode, which records at a wider angle. An illustrative example of the pertinent

image is presented in Figure 3a. The second is the 120 Hz mode, which records a narrower area but has a higher Hz value. The camera image of the relevant mode is shown in Figure 3b.

Fig. 3: Experiment Setup Screenshots

3.2 Image Stitching Techniques

In order to stitch sequential images, it is first necessary to mask the object, separate the background outside the object, and understand the difference between consecutive frames. In light of the aforementioned considerations, a number of methods have been subjected to examination and testing.

The initial method under consideration is the Frame Differences approach. The Frame Differences method represents a computational approach to the identification of an object's motion [16]. The implementation of this algorithm facilitates the differentiation of an object's movement within its surrounding environment [16]. Background subtraction represents an effective method for further improving frame differences, thereby enhancing the algorithm's overall precision and effectiveness [16].

Fig. 4: Frame Difference Results

A comparison of the resulting image when the method is applied is presented in Figure 4. The image on the left of the figure depicts the output, wherein the differences are represented in white after the frames have been differentiated. The image on the right, in contrast, illustrates the instantaneous frame. Despite the discernible discrepancy in the object’s movement direction, the temperature variations resulting from its motion are also apparent. This complexity posed a challenge in combining the disparate elements and hindered the method’s optimal functioning.

An additional method of application is SIFT (Scale Invariant Feature Transform) [17]. This method facilitates the detection and mapping of local features within the image [17]. Initially, the features are identified within the reference image. Subsequently, the features present in the new image are identified and key points are established [17]. The key points of the preceding image are then compared with those of the current image, with feature matching performed based on the Euclidean distance of the feature vectors [17]. From the comprehensive set of matches, subsets of key points that concur on the object and its location, scale, and orientation in the novel image are identified in order to filter out optimal matches [17]. Figure 5 depicts the output image resulting from the application of the SIFT algorithm to the test data set. Consequently, the key points are confused due to the absence of distinctive features in the thermal image of the object. Consequently, as illustrated in Figure 5, a point on the left side of the object can be matched with a key point on the right side of the subsequent image. Despite the application of the filter, an insufficient number of high-quality matches were identified for the purpose of stitching.

Fig. 5: SIFT Matching Results

In light of the insights gleaned from the deployment of the Frame Difference and SIFT methodologies, it was deemed prudent to integrate the segments extracted from a specific region of sequential frames with the assessment of the object’s progression. This led to the inception of the algorithmic development process.

3.3 Algorithm Development

In the initial phase of the development process, background subtraction was conducted as a preliminary step. The background was modified to black in accordance with the temperature color palette of the object. Subsequently, masking was conducted on the incoming frame, and contour detection was performed through this mask. The location of the boundaries of the object on the image is indicated by the contours. Subsequently, the aforementioned contours are collated into a list. Subsequently, the coordinates of the center point of the detected object are extracted from the relevant contour list at the specified moment. The aforementioned coordinate data allows for the instantaneous position of the detected object to be determined.

Another crucial aspect of the stitching process is the angle between the camera and the moving object. In the environment where the real data is received, the camera observes the plane in which the object is moving at an angle of approximately 45 degrees. This results in a discrepancy in perspective, whereby a regular rectangular shape is perceived as a trapezoid. Consequently, perspective correction is conducted during the merging of the sections captured. Furthermore, to mitigate the perspective effect, the slices are extracted from the bottom of the image, thereby ensuring consistency between the slices.

Fig. 6: Stitch Algorithm Flow Diagram

The cost-effective operation of the Stitch algorithm is also a factor that is taken into consideration. In order for the algorithm to function in a selective manner, only specific regions of the image are subject to control. In order to facilitate the operation of the algorithm, pre-defined regions of fixed height and width are created at the bottom and top of the image. The Y-axis coordinate of the detected object is evaluated to ascertain whether it enters these regions. Once the object has entered the designated bottom region, the extent of its progress is calculated, and a slice is then extracted from the object at the calculated position. Moreover, the color average of the pixels in the bottom region is employed to ascertain whether an object is still traversing it. Upon reaching a pixel color average of complete blackness, the stitch algorithm is terminated. The flowchart of the algorithm is presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 7: Axis Location per Frame Graph and Image Stitch Algorithm Output

Figure 7 illustrates the output of the stitch algorithm, with the tables on the left displaying the coordinates of the center point of the detected object on the Y and X axes, and the tables on the right displaying the detected object, its center point, and the upper and lower regions.

4 Results

One of the issues to be addressed in the conclusion is the determination of the appropriate Y-axis progression for the stitched image sections. It has been established that an excess of progression during the stitching process can result in the emergence of repeat patterns within the final image. Conversely, an insufficient amount of progression may result in the image being perceived as shorter than the actual object. For additional context, please refer to Figures 8a and 8b, which illustrate related examples. The output obtained with the optimal value yielded by the algorithm following the calculation for the sectioned region is illustrated in Figure 9b. As can be observed in Figure 9b, the repeat pattern commences at the base of the merged sections. Moreover, the absence of perspective correction results in the formation of jagged joints in the output image. This necessitates the implementation of perspective correction to ensure optimal visualization of the output. Figure 9a illustrates an example of output without perspective correction.

As with the repetition pattern issue, it is crucial to comprehend that the quantity of progress is accurately calculated in order to ascertain the source of the challenges encountered. Figure 10 illustrates the algorithm's performance on actual test data, with progress calculated on the Y-axis. As illustrated in the graph, the progression trend of the position/frame resembles that of a smoothly decelerating object over time. This phenomenon can be attributed to the camera's angle of observation, whereby as the object advances, the camera perceives a greater distance at an angle, resulting in a corresponding reduction in calculated progress. This is evident in the observed outcomes.

Fig. 8: Comparison Amount Of Advance Level

Fig. 9: Comparison Of Perspective Correction

Fig. 10: Y-axis Position Graph of Center of Moving Object

$$AdvanceRatio = 100 * \frac{YaxisPosition_t - YaxisPosition_{t-1}}{YaxisPosition_t} \quad (1)$$

One of the challenges in analyzing the results is the possibility of frame jumps in the incoming image. To determine whether any frame skips have occurred, Equation 1 is employed. This formula calculates the rate at which the moving object advances to the next position as a percentage. It was also determined that there was a skip in the third and eighth frames. Furthermore, the advancement rate of the object exhibited a decline contingent on the angle. The results are presented in graphical form in Figure 11.

Fig. 11: Percentage Advance Rate Graph per Frame

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The development of the image stitching algorithm was initiated with the objective of identifying solutions to the inherent constraints. In this context, the constraints were identified through an examination of the actual production environment, and the location of the camera was selected accordingly. The camera was positioned to enable the entire object to be observed. However, due to the fact that the object in question was larger than the field of view of the camera, image stitching was necessary.

As no real data was available, an artificial test environment was constructed. In the test environment, data were collected in accordance with the constraints that would be encountered in a real-world setting. It was determined that the camera is unable to capture the entire object, that the camera must view the object at an angle, and that the object must be warmer than the environment. The test data obtained from this test environment formed the basis for the development of the method.

Two distinct image stitching techniques were evaluated for their efficacy in detecting the object and identifying shared regions. The initial approach involved stitching different areas using the frame difference method. However, the fluctuations in the temperature data due to motion impeded the generation of a comprehensive cross-section, even with the application of filtering techniques. Another technique, SIFT, is employed to identify distinctive features within the thermal image data. However, given the similarity between the features within the thermal image, achieving a high degree of matching is not sufficient for the purpose of stitching.

Based on the experience gained from these techniques, the stitching process entailed the selection of sections from a specific area of the image, contingent on the detection and movement of the object.

Once the image stitching algorithm had been developed in the test environment, it was tested using actual data, with the area coordinates updated according to the real data. The results of the testing phase indicate that the algorithm should be modified to more accurately calculate the object's motion and support this calculation with artificial intelligence in future studies. Moreover, it would be beneficial to enhance the calculation of the speed reduction rate due to the angle.

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